

Attitude on Guidance and Counseling and Help-Seeking Among Selected LUC In First District of Oriental Mindoro

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Abstract

This study explored the relationship between students' attitudes on guidance and counseling services and their help-seeking behavior in selected Local Universities and Colleges (LUCs) in Oriental Mindoro. The objective was to examine how awareness, perception, and value of guidance services influence students' willingness to seek help. Using an embedded mixed-methods design, the research gathered data from first- and second-year students through a Likert-scale survey and qualitative responses. Quantitative data were analyzed for mean scores and correlations, while qualitative responses provided context to attitudes and experiences.

Results showed that students generally held favorable attitudes toward guidance services,

especially for academic support, but gaps remained in awareness and comfort discussing personal or sensitive issues. A positive relationship was found between favorable attitudes and actual help-seeking behavior across academic, personal, and social concerns. Based on the findings, the researcher developed a multi-component initiative aimed at improving awareness, trust, and engagement in guidance services. The study concludes with a recommendation for culturally grounded, student-centered programs that normalize help-seeking as a vital part of holistic development in higher education.

Keywords: *guidance and counseling, help-seeking behavior, mental health, cultural stigma, (LUC) local universities and colleges*

INTRODUCTION

Guidance and counseling services are integral components of student support systems in higher education, designed to assist students in managing academic, personal, and social challenges. These services are essential for promoting mental health, resilience, and long-term well-being, particularly as students experience stress, anxiety, and emotional difficulties. However, despite the increasing global focus on mental health, a pervasive stigma surrounding counseling persists, particularly in the context of the Philippines. Cultural values, such as "kapuwa" (shared identity), as well as concerns over saving face, contribute to students' reluctance to seek professional help, with many opting instead for informal support from family and peers (Menon, 2025). Additionally, misconceptions about the nature of counseling, often perceived as a resource for only severe issues, further deter students from utilizing these services (Laltoog, 2024).

While the implementation of the Mental Health Act of 2018 has mandated the integration of mental health services within educational institutions, cultural barriers and stigma continue to impede the effective utilization of guidance and counseling resources. This study seeks to examine the relationship between students' attitudes toward guidance and counseling services and their help-seeking behaviors, specifically exploring factors such as awareness, perception, and the value placed on these services. It also investigates the moderating role of demographic variables, including age, sex, and year level, in this relationship. The findings aim to provide a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing students' help-seeking behavior, thereby offering actionable insights for enhancing the accessibility and effectiveness of guidance and counseling services in higher education settings

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Research Design

This research utilized an embedded mixed-methods design described by Filiou et al., (2025), which involves the simultaneous gathering and evaluation of both quantitative and qualitative data, with one type given priority. In this case, quantitative data were prioritized in examining students' attitudes toward guidance and counseling services, as well as their help-seeking behavior. The qualitative data were complemented with quantitative findings by offering deeper insight into participants' responses regarding both variables. This design allows a comprehensive understanding of how students' attitudes influenced their willingness to seek counseling. By integrating both types of data, the study has offered a more clear comprehension on how students perceived and interacted with counseling services, turning light on the factors that shaped their help-seeking behaviour

Participants

This study was conducted in the First District of Oriental Mindoro, Philippines, particularly within the local universities and colleges (LUCs) in the mentioned district. These institutions were selected to provide a broad representation of the student population in the region.

LUC	Population (1st and 2nd Year)	Sample
Baco Community College	515	123
Colegio de Naujan	362	87
Colegio de Puerto Galera	198	48
Pola Community College	198	48
Total	1273	306

Instruments

The research instrument was self-constructed. It underwent expert validation to ensure both its validity and reliability. It was constructed with three main parts. The first part focused on the profile information of the respondents, including age, sex, and year level. The second portion assessed their attitudes toward guidance and counseling services. It consists of 10 items for each of the following indicators: awareness, perception, and value. On the other hand, the third part focused on help-seeking behavior, with 10 items each for academic, personal, and social concerns. Additionally, a set of 20 guide questions was included to explore qualitative data, providing deeper understandings into the participants' perspectives and experiences.

Procedure

Before data gathering, the researcher secured a request letter endorsed by the Dean of Graduate Studies at Mindoro State University and submitted it to the college administrators of various Local Universities and Colleges (LUCs) in the First District of Oriental Mindoro. After obtaining their approval, the departments were notified to help identify qualified student respondents. The research instrument's reliability was tested using the test-retest method and Pearson correlation. Experts reviewed the content for validity, while language and subject matter experts ensured the Filipino version was accurate and culturally appropriate. Coordination with program heads at approved institutions finalized the survey schedule. Informed consent forms were distributed to participants, ensuring voluntary participation and confidentiality. Data collection was supported by faculty members, with interviews conducted via Google Meet where needed.

After transcribing responses, each institution verified the data's authenticity. Descriptive statistics and Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient were used for data analysis. Following review and refinement, the study was submitted for formal evaluation and shared with administrators and guidance offices to improve counseling services. Copies were also distributed to stakeholders to support the enhancement of guidance project.

Data Analysis

Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze and interpret the data in this study. Frequency and percentage were applied to describe the demographic profile of the respondents. To determine the level of students' beliefs in guidance and counseling services and their help-seeking behavior, the weighted mean was utilized. Spearman Rho correlation was employed to assess the strength and direction of association between students' profile and their beliefs and behaviors related to guidance services. Additionally, moderation analysis was conducted to examine whether a third variable influenced the relationship between students' attitudes toward counseling services and their help-seeking behavior.

RESULTS

3.1. Profile of the Students

The participants in this study were selected based on their demographic characteristics, specifically age, gender, and year level. Understanding these factors helps contextualize their attitudes toward guidance and counseling services and help-seeking behavior.

3.1.1. Age

The majority of the respondents (54.58%) are aged 18 to 19 years, followed by 37.91% who are between 20 to 22 years old. A smaller portion (5.23%) are aged 23 to 25, and only 2.29% are 26 years or older. This reflects a predominantly young college-age student population.

Table 3.1.1.
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Profile of the students
in terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
18-19	167	54.58%
20-22	116	37.91%
23-25	16	5.23%

26-above	7	2.29%
Total	306	100.00%

3.1.2. Gender

The sample showed a significant gender disparity, with 65.36% of participants identifying as female, and 32.35% as male.

Table 3.1.2.
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Profile of the students in terms of Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	99	32.35%
Female	200	65.36%
Others	7	2.29%
Total	306	100.00%

3.1.2. Year Level

The majority of students (54.90%) were first-year students, while 45.10% were second-year students.

Table 1.3
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Profile of the students in terms of Year-level

Year-level	Frequency	Percentage
1 st Year	168	54.90%
2 nd Year	138	45.10%
Total	306	100.00%

3.2. Attitudes on Guidance and Counseling Services

This section explores students' attitudes toward guidance and counseling services in terms of awareness, perception, and value. The results draw from both quantitative survey data and qualitative interview responses, providing a well-rounded understanding of student experiences.

3.2.1. Awareness

The students' awareness of guidance and counseling services shows a generally positive trend, especially regarding the office's existence (mean = 3.36), available programs (mean = 3.32–3.38), and its role in student well-being. However, the lowest-rated item, "I know the process of how to avail the services," had a mean of 2.62, indicating that while students are aware of the services, they lack clarity on how to access them. Interview data supported this, with some students noting they had heard of the services but were unsure of the process (P1). Some were more familiar due to orientation or personal experiences (P8), but overall, there was a gap between awareness and practical engagement.

Table 3.2.1.
Attitude on Guidance and Counseling services of the students
in terms of Awareness

Awareness	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I know about the existence of a guidance and counseling office at my school.	3.36	Very Favorable
2. I am informed about the guidance and counseling services available to students	3.31	Very Favorable
3. I have knowledge about the types of services offered by the guidance and counseling office.	3.32	Very Favorable
4. I am aware that career counseling services are available to help with course and career decisions.	3.32	Very Favorable
5. I am familiar with the individuals providing the guidance and counseling services.	3.29	Very Favorable
6. I am aware of the availability of the counseling service.	3.08	Very Favorable
7. I know about group counseling sessions offered by the guidance office.	3.16	Very Favorable
8. I am familiar with the process in availing services	2.62	Favorable
9. I know that the guidance office provides referral services to other professionals or organizations when needed.	3.27	Very Favorable
10. I understand that the guidance office conducts programs or activities to enhance student well-being and development.	3.38	Very Favorable
Average	3.21	Very Favorable

3.2.2. Perception

Students generally hold a favorable perception of guidance and counseling services, reflected in an overall mean score of 3.30. High-scoring items included perceptions of the office as a supportive environment and counselors as approachable. Interviews affirmed this, with students describing the office as a safe space for emotional support (P1, P4). These responses suggest that stigma around help-seeking is decreasing, aligning with Othman and Hashim (2024), who found that positive perceptions increase service utilization. Bandura's self-efficacy theory and Ayeni et al. (2024) also support the idea that accessible, non-judgmental support enhances students' coping and resilience.

However, not all perceptions were equally strong. The item on receiving decision-making resources scored lower (mean = 2.81), and some interviewees expressed hesitation or lingering stigma. One student noted feelings of not belonging (P5), while another associated guidance with punishment (P10).

Institutional data showed variation, with Colegio de Puerto Galera scoring highest in perception (3.38), followed by Naujan (3.37), Baco (3.31), and Pola (2.99). While all scores fall within a favorable range, these differences indicate uneven effectiveness in how guidance services are communicated and understood across campuses.

Table 3.2.2.
Attitude on Guidance and Counseling services of the students
in terms of Perception

Perception	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I view guidance and counseling services as supportive environment.	3.38	Very Favorable
2. I believe that the guidance office provides resources to help students make informed decisions	2.81	Favorable
3. I think that counseling services are a good resource for students who need personal or psychological support.	3.39	Very Favorable
4. I believe that guidance and counseling services are equipped with necessary resources and designed to provide effective assistance to students.	3.20	Very Favorable
5. I perceive the guidance and counseling services as being inclusive.	3.26	Very Favorable
6. I find the school counselors to be approachable when seeking assistance.	3.42	Very Favorable
7. I believe that the counseling services can effectively address the issues I face.	3.34	Very Favorable
8. I believe that the counseling services offered are sufficient to meet the diverse needs of students.	3.39	Very Favorable
9. I believe that guidance and counseling services contribute to the overall development of students.	3.39	Very Favorable
10. I view guidance and counseling services as having a crucial role in fostering a positive school environment.	3.39	Very Favorable
Average	3.30	Very Favorable

3.2.3. Value

Students place high value on guidance and counseling services, with an overall mean score of 3.37—falling within the “Very Favorable” range. Notably, the item “I believe that the safe space the guidance office offers is important” (mean = 3.39) underscores the office's emotional significance. One student shared, “Importante po siya... Para siyang alternative kung ayaw mong magsabi sa kaibigan o pamilya” (P1), reflecting how the office serves as a vital refuge for those facing personal challenges. Another highly rated item, “I value the services provided by the guidance office” (mean = 3.45), highlights appreciation for both the service and counselor demeanor. A student remarked, “Approachable naman po yung mga guidance counselor... kahit mahiyain ka o tahimik, lalapitan ka nila” (P5), reinforcing that approachability fosters engagement. Miller (2025) supports this, noting that warmth and responsiveness encourage help-seeking, while Fiorentino (2025) warns that distant staff can deter students.

The guidance office's role in inclusivity was also recognized, with a 3.34 mean score for promoting an inclusive environment. One student emphasized its relevance for Indigenous Peoples: “Most of the

students po ay mga IPs... helpful po ang pagkakaroon ng guidance and counseling” (P3). Institutional data showed consistent results: Colegio de Puerto Galera scored highest, and Pola Community College the lowest, though all remained within the favorable range. This consistency affirms that across campuses, students view guidance as essential. Both quantitative and qualitative data reveal that students see guidance not just as a service, but as a cornerstone of emotional, academic, and social support.

Table 3.2.3.
Attitude on Guidance and Counseling services of the students
in terms of Value

Value	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I think the guidance and counseling services offered in our school are important for students' well-being.	3.31	Very Favorable
2. I support the programs of the guidance and counseling office because I recognize that they are essential.	3.25	Very Favorable
3. I value the importance of having a guidance office in our school.	3.45	Very Favorable
4. I value the services provided by the guidance office.	3.45	Very Favorable
5. I enjoy participating in guidance programs that promote personal growth.	3.37	Very Favorable
6. I appreciate the role of guidance and counseling services in supporting students' well-being.	3.43	Very Favorable
7. I believe that the safe space the guidance office offers is important.	3.39	Very Favorable
8. I believe guidance and counseling services are essential in promoting an inclusive school environment.	3.34	Very Favorable
9. I believe in the importance of guidance and counseling services in helping students build healthy relationships.	3.30	Very Favorable
10. I recognize the importance of guidance and counseling services in increasing awareness and providing mental health support for students.	3.36	Very Favorable
Average	3.37	Very Favorable

3.3. Help-Seeking Behavior

This section examines student behavior and willingness to seek support in academic, personal, and social contexts. It integrates quantitative data with qualitative insights gathered from focus group discussions, revealing both the strengths and limitations of current help-seeking practices among students.

3.3.1 Academic

Students showed a very favorable level of help-seeking behavior for academic issues (mean = 3.28). They expressed willingness to consult counselors for academic goal setting and career alignment, an indication of gradually improving perceptions regarding openness to seeking professional guidance and support.

Table 3.3.1
Help-seeking behavior of the students
in terms of Academic concern

Academic	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I am willing to consult the guidance counselor for help in setting academic goals.	3.31	Very Favorable
2. I am willing to seek guidance services when I struggle to manage my study habits.	3.24	Very Favorable
3. I am willing to approach the guidance counselor for seeking advice on improving my grades.	3.27	Very Favorable
4. I am willing to participate in counseling services offered to improve my academic performance.	3.30	Very Favorable
5. I am interested to attend workshops or seminars organized by the guidance office related to academic success.	3.30	Very Favorable
6. I am willing to discuss my academic difficulties with the guidance counselor.	3.26	Very Favorable
7. I am willing to seek advice to align my academic performance with my career goals.	3.31	Very Favorable
8. I am willing to request help from the counselor in developing a study plan.	3.26	Very Favorable
9. I am open to participating in guidance programs to learn techniques for handling academic pressure.	3.32	Very Favorable
10. I am comfortable seeking help from the guidance office for test-taking strategies.	3.25	Very Favorable
Average	3.28	Very Favorable

3.3.2 Personal

Help-seeking behavior for personal concerns was also very favorable, with an average mean of 3.19. Students are willing to discuss emotional well-being, though there is less openness in discussing family issues (mean = 2.73).

Table 3.3.2
Help-seeking behavior of the students
in terms of Personal concern

Personal	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I am willing to ask the guidance counselor for help with personal, sensitive topics.	3.23	Very Favorable
2. I am willing to approach the counselor to discuss family-related concern.	2.73	Favorable
3. I am open to using guidance services for support if I face personal challenges, like financial problems.	3.20	Very Favorable
4. I am open to seeking help from guidance and counseling services to improve my self-worth.	3.18	Very Favorable
5. I am willing to seek advice from the counselor in maintaining emotional well-being.	3.31	Very Favorable
6. I am willing to participate in personal development programs offered by the guidance office.	3.28	Very Favorable
7. I am willing to ask for support from the guidance counselor in developing skills to deal with emotional difficulties.	3.25	Very Favorable
8. I am willing to engage with guidance and counseling services to help me cope with personal challenges.	3.24	Very Favorable
9. I would use the guidance office's resources if I needed support with my self-esteem.	3.25	Very Favorable
10. I am open to having sessions with the counselor to discuss personal issues that I cannot share with others.	3.23	Very Favorable
Average	3.19	Very Favorable

3.3.3. Social

Students showed a very favorable attitude toward seeking help for social concerns (mean = 3.22). They are especially open to programs enhancing social skills but less inclined to seek help when feeling isolated or struggling with communication.

Table 3.3.3
Help-seeking behavior of the students
in terms of social concern

Social	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I am willing to seek guidance from the counselor on improving relationships with others.	3.26	Very Favorable
2. I am willing to approach the guidance office for help in resolving conflicts with others.	2.84	Favorable
3. I am willing to attend programs organized by the guidance office to enhance my social skills.	3.34	Very Favorable

4. I am willing to seek help from counseling services, if I have trouble working with group members.	3.29	Very Favorable
5. I am open to discussing my difficulty in interacting with others with the guidance counselor.	3.26	Very Favorable
6. I am willing to ask the counselor for guidance to smoothly improve my personal communication with my peers and teachers.	3.28	Very Favorable
7. I am willing to participate in peer mentoring or support groups facilitated by the guidance office.	3.30	Very Favorable
8. I am open to seeking help from the guidance office in managing social differences.	3.29	Very Favorable
9. I am open to using counseling services to address this feeling, if I feel isolated.	3.18	Very Favorable
10. I am open to availing guidance and counseling services to develop more effective communication strategies	3.18	Very Favorable
Average	3.22	Very Favorable

3.4. Significant relationship between Attitude on Guidance and Counseling services and Help-seeking Behavior

A significant positive correlation exists between students' attitudes, across awareness, perception, and value, and their help-seeking behavior for academic, personal, and social concerns. This suggests that students with more favorable attitudes are more likely to seek help from the guidance office.

Table 3.4
Correlational Analysis between Attitude on Guidance and Counseling services and Help-seeking Behavior

Spearman's Correlations

Attitude	Help-Seeking	Spearman's rho	P	Interpretation
Awareness	- Academic	0.598	< .001	Significant
	- Personal	0.551	< .001	Significant
	- Social	0.64	< .001	Significant
Perception	- Academic	0.644	< .001	Significant
	- Personal	0.601	< .001	Significant
	- Social	0.62	< .001	Significant
Value	- Academic	0.621	< .001	Significant
	- Personal	0.573	< .001	Significant
	- Social	0.585	< .001	Significant

* p < .05, ** p < .01, *** p < .001

3.5. Moderating Effect of Profile Variables

While the core findings established significant relationships between attitudes and help-seeking behaviors, further analysis is required to comprehensively determine whether age, sex, or year level significantly moderate these relationships.

Table 3. 5.1 Moderation Estimates

	Estimate	SE	Z	p
ATTITUDE	0.84267	0.04375	19.261	< .001
AGE	0.00527	0.00759	0.694	0.487
ATTITUDE * AGE	-0.00351	0.01867	-0.188	0.851

Table 3.5.2 Moderation Estimates

	Estimate	SE	Z	p
ATTITUDE	0.84267	0.04375	19.261	< .001
AGE	0.00527	0.00759	0.694	0.487
ATTITUDE * AGE	-0.00351	0.01867	-0.188	0.851

Table 3.5.3. Moderation Estimates

	Estimate	SE	Z	p
ATTITUDE	0.8365	0.0439	19.039	< .001
YEAR LEVEL	0.0300	0.0346	0.867	0.386
ATTITUDE * YEAR LEVEL	-0.0268	0.0927	-0.290	0.772

3.6. Proposed Guidance Project to address the result of the study

Based on the findings, a comprehensive initiative titled "From Confusion to Confidence: Strengthening Student Support through Strategic Guidance Initiatives" is proposed. It includes six key components: "From How? To Wow!" to improve awareness of guidance services; Project GABAY (Guidance and Assistance for Better Awareness and Youth Empowerment), to enhance perception and trust; Project VALYOU (Valuing You through Guidance) to reinforce the value of guidance in student growth; Project PAGASA (Promoting Academic Guidance and Support Access) for academic support; Project CARE (Counseling Assistance and Resilience Enhancement), for personal and emotional wellness; and Project CONNECT (College-Oriented Nurturing Network Enhancing Connection and Togetherness), to boost social skills and peer interaction. These targeted programs aim to promote well-being, academic success, and stronger student engagement with guidance services.

DISCUSSION

The study explored students' attitudes toward guidance and counseling services, focusing on their demographic profile, awareness, perceptions, and help-seeking behavior. Most participants were young, with 54.58% aged 18-19, and the majority were female (65.36%), reflecting global trends in higher education enrollment (Clancy & O'Sullivan, 2020). The majority of students (54.90%) were first-year students, which aligns with national trends in college enrollment (CHED, 2023; PSA, 2022). In terms of awareness, students generally recognized the existence and role of the guidance office, but the process for accessing services was unclear, with an average score of 2.62 for "knowing how to avail the services." This gap between awareness and engagement was echoed in interviews, where some students expressed uncertainty about how to access support. While perceptions of the guidance services were largely positive, with a mean score of 3.30, some students still held negative associations, such as viewing counseling as a form of punishment or feeling a lack of belonging. Despite these concerns, students valued the services highly (mean = 3.37), particularly as a safe space for emotional support. Many students emphasized the importance of the guidance office, particularly for those facing personal challenges like family issues or isolation (Saruchera et al., 2025; Martineau, 2025).

In terms of help-seeking behavior, students showed a favorable willingness to seek support across academic, personal, and social domains. For academic concerns, students displayed strong help-seeking behavior (mean = 3.28), particularly for goal setting and career guidance. Personal help-seeking behavior was also positive (mean = 3.19), though students were less open to discussing family issues (mean = 2.73). Socially, students were generally open to seeking help, especially for enhancing social skills (mean = 3.22), but less so when dealing with isolation or communication challenges. Overall, the study highlighted that while students have a favorable view of guidance services, there are still barriers, including limited awareness and lingering stigma, which impact their willingness to engage fully with these resources (Leeman et al., 2024; Hopp et al., 2025; Goodwin et al., 2022; Soh et al., 2024).

The study revealed a significant positive correlation between students' attitudes toward guidance and counseling services, specifically in terms of awareness, perception, and value and their help-seeking behavior across academic, personal, and social concerns. This finding suggests that students with more favorable attitudes toward guidance services are more likely to seek help from the guidance office. However, further analysis is needed to determine whether demographic factors such as age, gender, and year level moderate these relationships. Previous research aligns with this conclusion, with Sum et al. (2024) noting that students are more likely to use counseling services when they view them as beneficial and trustworthy, regardless of their age or year level. This is consistent with the findings of Aruta et al. (2023), who observed that help-seeking behavior does not significantly vary across age groups. The central factor driving students to seek help seems to be their perception of guidance services rather than their demographic characteristics. Similarly, Yang et al. (2024) found that students with positive perceptions of professional psychological support are more likely to use those services, regardless of gender, though prior counseling experience and awareness also play a role. This aligns with the findings of Sharp et al. (2024), who pointed out that men often prefer informal support from friends or family, while women are more inclined to seek formal counseling. However, both studies agree that attitudes toward help-seeking are more influential than gender alone. This supports earlier research by Gentry et al. (2024), which emphasized that personal attitudes, such as emotional readiness, stigma, and access to services—are stronger predictors of help-seeking behavior than demographic factors like year level.

Given these insights, the study proposes a comprehensive initiative called *"From Confusion to Confidence: Strengthening Student Support through Strategic Guidance Initiatives."* This initiative includes six key components aimed at increasing student engagement with guidance services and promoting overall well-being. The first component, "From How? To Wow!", seeks to improve awareness of guidance services. Project GABAY (Guidance and Assistance for Better Awareness and Youth Empowerment) focuses on

enhancing students' perceptions and building trust in these services. Project VALYOU (Valuing You through Guidance) emphasizes the importance of guidance in student development. Project PAGASA (Promoting Academic Guidance and Support Access) is dedicated to providing academic guidance and support, while Project CARE (Counseling Assistance and Resilience Enhancement) aims to foster emotional well-being and resilience. Lastly, Project CONNECT (College-Oriented Nurturing Network Enhancing Connection and Togetherness) will work to enhance social skills and peer relationships. These targeted initiatives are designed to promote academic success, emotional health, and stronger student engagement with guidance services.

Furthermore, the study focuses solely on first- and second-year students from local universities and colleges in the first district of Oriental Mindoro, including Colegio de Puerto Galera, Baco Community College, Colegio de Naujan, and Pola Community College. Therefore, the results may not be generalizable to other regions or institutions. Additionally, the data collected was self-reported, which may introduce bias, and the study captures information at one point in time, not accounting for potential changes over time. External factors, such as changes in school policies or societal attitudes toward mental health, were also not considered. To gain a more comprehensive understanding of students' experiences, individual interviews were conducted alongside the survey data, helping to fill gaps and provide real-life context to the findings.

Conclusion

This research highlights the crucial role that positive attitudes toward guidance and counseling services play in influencing college students' help-seeking behavior. The student population, predominantly young and female, is primarily composed of first- and second-year students, a stage in their academic and personal development where support services are particularly important. While students generally exhibit favorable attitudes toward guidance services, especially in terms of awareness, perception, and value, gaps persist in their understanding of how to access these services and in seeking help for more personal challenges, such as family issues or feelings of isolation. Help-seeking behavior was positive across academic, personal, and social concerns, with the strongest inclination toward seeking academic support. However, students showed some hesitancy in disclosing more vulnerable issues, such as family struggles or isolation. A significant positive correlation was found between students' attitudes and their help-seeking behavior, emphasizing the need to foster awareness, trust, and the perceived value of guidance services. Although demographic factors like age, sex, and year level did not conclusively moderate this relationship, further research is needed to understand their potential influence. In response to these findings, the study proposes the "From Confusion to Confidence" initiative, which aims to improve awareness, perception, and engagement with guidance services through targeted programs such as Project GABAY, Project VALYOU, and Project CONNECT, ultimately promoting student well-being, academic success, and personal development. For future research, conducting longitudinal studies that examine how demographic factors such as age, sex, and year level may influence attitudes and help-seeking behavior over time would offer deeper insights into specific student subgroups that may need tailored interventions. Additionally, future research should evaluate the implementation and effectiveness of the proposed guidance initiatives to assess their impact on students' attitudes and help-seeking behavior.

REFERENCES

- Aruta, J.J.B.R., Maria, A. & Mascarenhas, J. Self-compassion promotes mental help-seeking in older, not in younger, counselors. *Curr Psychol* 42, 18615–18625 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-022-03054-6>
- Ayeni, O. O., Chisom, O. N., Al Hamad, N. M., Osawaru, B., & Adewusi, O. E. (2024). Enhancing STEM education through emotional intelligence and counseling techniques. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 21(2), 903-916.
- Clancy, P., & O’Sullivan, S. (2020). Gender parity in higher education enrolments: trends and paradoxes. *Irish Educational Studies*, 39(3), 337–354. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03323315.2020.1779107>
- Commission on Higher Education MIMAROPA. (2024). CHED MIMAROPA Statistical Bulletin for AY 2022–2023. CHED Regional Office IV-B. Retrieved from https://mimaropa.ched.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/CHED_MIMAROPA-Stat-Bull-22-23FINAL.pdf
- Filiou, R. P., Couture, M., Lussier, M., Aboujaoudé, A., Paré, G., Giroux, S., ... & Bier, N. (2025). Decision-Making Process of Home and Social Care Professionals Using Telemonitoring of Activities of Daily Living for Risk Assessment: Embedded Mixed Methods Multiple-Case Study. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 27, e64713.
- Gentry, N. M. (2024). Rural Mental Health Counselors’ Descriptions of Challenges Encountered During the Process of State Licensure (Doctoral dissertation, University of Arizona Global Campus).
- Goodwin, J., Savage, E., & O’Donovan, A. (2022). “I Personally Wouldn’t Know Where to Go”: Adolescents’ Perceptions of Mental Health Services. *Journal of Adolescent Research*, 39(5), 1384-1412. <https://doi.org/10.1177/07435584221076056> (Original work published 2024)
- Gregorio, Candelario., Cristela, Mae, Candelario., Reagan, Joseph, Villanueva. (2024). Telepsychiatry Enables Better Mental Health Care Access in a Southern Philippines Hospital: a Mixed Methods Outcome Evaluation. *The Philippine journal of science*, 153(4) doi: 10.56899/153.04.15
- Hopp, F. P., Thomas, S. A., Keys, F., & Ward, M. (2025). Predictors of Service Awareness: Results from a Community Survey in an Urban Area. *Journal of Gerontological Social Work*, 1-16.
- Laltoog, B. B. (2024). Support System of Transnational Families in Guinzadan Bauko Mountain Province Philippines. *Diversitas Journal*, 9(1), 220-251.
- Leeman, J., Rohweder, C., Lafata, J. E., Wangen, M., Ferrari, R., Shea, C. M., ... & Toles, M. (2024). A streamlined approach to classifying and tailoring implementation strategies: recommendations to speed the translation of research to practice. *Implementation Science Communications*, 5(1), 65.
- Menon, S. (2025). Filipino American cultural beliefs, perceptions of autism, and help-seeking behaviors.
- Othman, M. H., & Hashim, A. F. M. (2024). Supporting orang asli students: Counseling in school contexts. *Quantum Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 5(4), 150-166.
- Philippine Statistics Authority. (2023, August 4). Four out of five children aged 5 to 24 years were attending school: School Year 2022–2023. PSA. Retrieved from <https://psa.gov.ph/content/four-out-five-children-aged-5-24-years-were-attending-school-school-year-2022-2023>
- Soh, Y. L. (2024). Understanding public stigma and self-stigma on university students’ psychological distress in influencing help seeking behaviours (Doctoral dissertation, UTAR).
- Sharp, P., Zhu, P., Ogrodniczuk, J. S., McKenzie, S. K., Seidler, Z. E., Rice, S. M.; Oliffe, J. L. (2024). Men’s peer support for mental health challenges: future directions for research and practice. *Health Promotion International*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/heapro/daae046>
- Shefaly, Shorey., Jamie, Qiao, Xin, Ng., Verity, Chandelle, Liu., Y., Chan., C., Chee. (2024). Nurturing networks: A prospective longitudinal study of factors influencing help-seeking behaviours among mothers from low socioeconomic status.. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, doi: 10.1111/jan.16382
- Sum, M. Y., Chan, S. K. W., Tsui, H. K. H., & Wong, G. H. Y. (2024). Stigma towards mental illness, resilience, and help-seeking behaviours in undergraduate students in Hong Kong. *Early Intervention in Psychiatry*, 18(3), 181-189.

Yang, X., Hu, J., Zhang, B., Hua, D., Hu, D.,38; Li, H. (2024). The relationship between mental health literacy and professional psychological help-seeking behavior among Chinese college students: mediating roles of perceived social support and psychological help-seeking stigma. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1356435>